

Light Management in Upconverting Nanoparticles: Ultrasmall Core/Shell Architectures to Tune the Emission Color

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ABSTRACT: Ultrasmall NaGdF₄ nanoparticles with core/shell and core/shell/shell architectures have been synthesized following a microwave based thermolysis procedure, allowing us to rapidly obtain homogeneous nanoparticles compared to conventional heating. To analyze the possibilities of the proposed structure in terms of tuning the emission color, core and shells have been doped with different lanthanide ion pairs (either Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ and/or Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺) keeping them therefore spatially separated inside the different layers of the nanoparticles. Here, we demonstrate that the position of the dopants inside the nanoparticles affect the intensity of the different emission bands of the luminescing Tm³⁺ and Er³⁺ ions and show how it has a relevant effect on the overall emission color of the luminescence obtained after 975 nm excitation.

Since the last century, nanosized particles have elicited a great deal of excitement with the promise to bring forth a paradigm shift by provoking a technological (and biotechnological) transformation. In the vanguard of this push towards the nanoscale, luminescent nanoparticles have graduated from mere academic curiosity to being seriously considered for use in a plethora of applications¹⁻³. Perhaps their biggest impact will come in their use in biology where their nanometric dimensions similar to many biological structures, can potentially lead to their use in diverse applications such as optical probes for sensing, diagnosis and even therapeutics for a slate of diseases³⁻⁷. In many cases, this new generation of luminescent nanoparticles forms the nuclei of multifunctional nanoplatforms where two or more of the functions described above can be carried out (either sequentially or simultaneously) in one nanoscale platform^{8,9}.

Traditionally, many of these luminescent nanoparticles studied have been optically excited following a conventional route whereby ultraviolet (UV) or visible light emissions are observed following excitation with higher energy photons. This can lead to various complications since often biological samples have inherent chromophores or fluorophores that could emit light when excited with high-energy radiation^{10, 11}. Consequently, their presence generates a large background autofluorescence that complicates the detection of the emission from the nanoparticles unless more complex optical techniques are employed. Moreover, exciting with UV photons hinders the tissue penetration capabilities and can also irreversibly cause

photo-damage to the specimen under study, potentially limiting the scope of their possible applications.

Excitation with near-infrared (NIR) light could alleviate some of the problems associated with conventional high-energy light-excitation, especially considering that biological tissues have an optical transparency window in the NIR region (approximately 700-1000 nm)¹². Therefore, the possibility of using long wavelength (or low-energy) NIR light as an excitation source to generate shorter wavelength photons (either in the UV, visible, or even NIR ranges) is remarkably attractive for biological applications^{1, 2, 4, 13, 14}. For example, it becomes possible to use NIR light to trigger further photo-activated processes whereby currently only UV or blue light can be used, as is the case in photocatalysis, photothermal/photodynamic therapies or drug delivery^{1, 15}.

In this context, several materials have been proposed as nanoemitters using a NIR excitation strategy. Metal nanoparticles or semiconductor quantum dots are amongst the most explored materials for these applications^{16, 17}. However, to obtain visible emissions following NIR illumination requires, in this case, ultrafast excitation. This is due to the absence of available intermediate energy states, which implies that population of the excited state requires the simultaneous absorption of more than one photon¹⁸. This is, from the point of view of the applications, a clear economical drawback as these excitation sources can be very costly. Bearing in mind these facts, a different family of nanoparticles based on lanthanide-doped materials is currently being considered. In this case, a transparent nanocrystal, most commonly fluoride-based, is doped with a certain concentration of lanthanide ions. Due to the *4f* electronic configuration of

the lanthanides, with the valence electrons shielded by the filled outer $5s$, $6s$ and $5p$ shells, they add to the host matrix a series of available excited states at well-known fixed energies weakly dependent on the environment. These states can be used to promote electrons, in a ladder-like process, thereby making it possible to obtain higher energy emissions (in the UV, visible or even NIR) following NIR excitation.^{19, 20} Moreover, since the intermediate energy states used for this process, known as upconversion, are not only real states but they are also characteristic for their relatively long lifetimes, the higher energy emissions can be obtained from NIR excitation using inexpensive continuous wave diode lasers as the excitation source. This is in stark contrast, as mentioned, to the case of semiconductor or metal nanoparticles.

In the case of quantum dots and metal nanorods, the wavelength of the emission can be modified by changing the size or aspect ratio of the nanostructures, respectively. Conversely, for lanthanide-doped nanoparticles, size and shape have an effect on the intensity of the light emissions, but not on the obtained wavelengths. Instead, the “color” of the emission can be tuned by altering the specific lanthanide ions used as dopants or their concentrations. For instance, Er^{3+} ions are characteristic for their green and red emissions, while Tm^{3+} ions generally emit in the NIR, blue and ultraviolet range of the spectrum. In both cases, the upconversion process can be sensitized with Yb^{3+} ions, since the transitions associated to their single excited state allow for the absorption and emission of NIR photons (at circa 975 nm). Additionally, Yb^{3+} ions have a higher absorption cross section than Er^{3+} or Tm^{3+} at that wavelength, and are able to efficiently transfer energy both to Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} ions, thus triggering the upconversion processes that will generate higher energy light²¹.

Taking these into account, it would be possible to use one single NIR excitation source (at 975 nm) to excite a single nanoparticle doped with Yb^{3+} , Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} ions in order to obtain red (R), green (G) and blue (B) emissions. This lays the foundation for the development of a versatile RGB-based nanosystem that can provide a wide range of emission colors²². Unfortunately, managing the color of the resulting emission light is not a simple feat due to the multitude of energy transfer processes that can occur between lanthanide ions, which are strongly dependent on the distance separating the dopant ions, and thus, are strongly affected by the dopant concentration. For instance, in a tri-doped nanoparticle ($\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Tm}^{3+}$) the three needed emission colors, blue green and red would be present, but the relative intensities of the emissions would be difficult to control in order to tune the emission, since it will be strongly affected by the energy transfer processes from Er^{3+} to Er^{3+} and/or from Tm^{3+} to Tm^{3+} as well as the concomitant energy transfer processes between Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} ions that will quench certain emissions and enhance others, generally reducing the range of emission colors that can be obtained for lanthanide-doped nanoparticles²³⁻²⁶.

In this work, we develop a lanthanide-doped upconverting NaGdF_4 nanoparticle possessing a core/shell architecture with different dopants in the core and the shell. The goal is to spatially separate the Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} ions in order to reduce the transfer of energy between them. Furthermore, the nanoparticles are prepared using a modified thermal decomposition process that employs microwave-assisted heating rather than conventional heating. The use of microwave reactors is a very recent innovation for the synthesis of upconverting nanoparticles that yields the possibility of obtaining highly homogeneous particles, both from the morphological and structural point of view, and in a very short time frame²⁷⁻³¹. Until recently, microwave-assisted synthesis has successfully demonstrated the possibility of obtaining ultrasmall lanthanide-doped nanoparticles, but the synthesis of more complicated structures including core/shell nanoarchitectures has been a challenge. Here, we synthesize multi-layered nanostructures such as core/shell and core/shell/shell while investigating the ability to control the light output of the nanoparticles by segregating the luminescent lanthanide ions in individual portions of the nanoparticle.

With this ultimate goal, we performed a sequential process of up to three treatment steps in a microwave autoclave. The synthesis procedure for the lanthanide-doped nanoparticles was based on the thermal decomposition technique using metal trifluoroacetates as precursors³² that were dispersed in a 0.5:0.5:1 solution of oleic acid, oleylamine and 1-octadecene (Refer to the Supplementary Information for further details about the synthesis procedure). The selected concentrations of dopants are, in the first approach, ($[\text{Tm}^{3+}] = 0.2 \text{ mol\%/}[\text{Yb}^{3+}] = 20 \text{ mol\%}$) and ($[\text{Er}^{3+}] = 2 \text{ mol\%/}[\text{Yb}^{3+}] = 20 \text{ mol\%}$), since these values are in the range that have been demonstrated to be optimum to get intense blue emissions from Tm^{3+} ions and green emissions from Er^{3+} ions, respectively³³⁻³⁵.

The initial microwave-assisted synthesis of ultrasmall $\text{NaGdF}_4:\text{Tm}^{3+}$, Yb^{3+} nanoparticles took place in a tightly closed vessel for 10 min. at 300 °C, and yielded spherical and highly homogeneous nanoparticles with a size of $6.1 \pm 0.8 \text{ nm}$ (Figure 1A). Moreover, the XRD measurements, also shown in Figure 1, clearly showed that the nanoparticles crystallized in the α -phase (cubic phase) of NaGdF_4 . Subsequently, we added to the vessel containing the core-only $\text{NaGdF}_4:\text{Tm}^{3+}$, Yb^{3+} nanoparticles the necessary precursors to grow an active (i.e. luminescent) shell of $\text{NaGdF}_4:\text{Er}^{3+}$, Yb^{3+} , and treated the mix in the microwave during 10 min at 270 °C. Further TEM analysis (Figure 1B) demonstrated that the new nanoparticles kept the same spherical shape and crystal phase as the parent core-only nanoparticles. However, as expected, their average size was observed to be larger than in the previous case ($7.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$).

It is well known that growing an undoped (passive) shell around upconverting nanoparticles would increase the intensity of the upconverted luminescence because it isolates the active ions (sensitizers and activators) from

the environment³⁶⁻³⁸. Moreover, since the effect of the environment will not necessarily affect every dopant ion equally, it will also change the overall upconverted emission color. Aiming to analyze this effect, as a final step, we grew a third undoped layer of NaGdF₄ on the already synthesized core/shell nanoparticles by means of a third microwave step equivalent to the previous one, this time for one minute at 270 °C. The resulting nanoparticles are shown in Figure 1C. The final core/shell/shell upconverting nanoparticles still show a homogeneous spherical morphology and α crystal phase, but they possess an even larger size than previous (8.5 ± 0.8 nm). High resolution TEM was performed on these final core/shell/shell nanoparticles (Figure 1D) and nicely demonstrated that the particles were monocrystalline, with clearly visible lattice fringes and did not show any interphases.

Figure 1. TEM micrographs of the nanoparticles obtained with NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ precursors (A), core/shell nanoparticles obtained from A adding NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ precursors (B) and the core/shell/shell nanoparticles obtained after the growth of an undoped NaGdF₄ shell over B (C). A higher magnification of these core/shell/shell particles is shown in (D). Below, the XRD patterns of each sample compared to the pattern for α -NaGdF₄ (JCPDS 00-027-0697) are shown.

To get a clearer idea of the size evolution of the nanoparticles after all the subsequent synthesis steps, the particle size distributions obtained after measuring several hundreds of particles from the TEM images were plotted in Figure 2. As it can be seen, in every case, single distributions are obtained, clearly demonstrating the homogeneity of the nanoparticles. This result supports the notion that after each successive growth process, one single type of nanoparticles is synthesized, since particle size distributions with two (or three) peaks would likely be obtained if the subsequent addition of precursors were creating new nuclei instead of growing a shell on the previous particles.

Figure 2. Size distribution of the upconverting nanoparticles obtained after each synthesis step. First NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ core, then NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ core with NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ shell, and finally NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ with two shells, NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ (inner shell) and undoped NaGdF₄ (outermost shell).

From Figure 2 it is also clear that the nanoparticles become larger after each growth step, initially starting from approximately 6 nm after the growth of the core-only nanoparticles to a final size of 8.5 nm for the core/shell/shell nanoparticles after the addition of two more sets of precursors. Thus, this size increase is also consistent with our hypothesis that the ultrasmall nanoparticles synthesized at the onset become the core in a core/shell structure after the second step, and these core/shell nanoparticles become the core/shell/shell structures after another addition of precursors.

To underscore the reproducibility of these results, the syntheses were repeated up to four times following the same protocol and using the same concentrations of dopants. In this way, average values of the nanoparticle diameters of 6.0 ± 0.2 nm for the core-only nanoparticles, 7.9 ± 0.4 nm for the core/shell nanoparticles and 8.9 ± 0.4 nm for the core/shell/shell nanoparticles were calculated. The errors in these values represent the standard deviation obtained for the average of the four averaged sizes, and they show that the size of the nanoparticles is to a large extent, the same in every synthesis.

As a further test, it was considered that since the nanoparticles were not washed between steps, the

possibility still persisted that any unreacted precursors remaining in the solvent could account for the growth of new nanoparticles. To test this hypothesis, some of the nanoparticles shown in Figure 1B (core/shell nanoparticles before washing) were heat treated in the microwave for 10 min at 270 °C, under the same conditions that were used to obtain the nanoparticles in Figure 1C (core/shell/shell), but without additional

precursors. In this experiment (Figure S1) a difference of 0.2 nm in the average size of the nanoparticles was found, a value that is within the experimental error and much smaller than the observed size increase of the nanoparticles when precursors are added to the solution. Therefore, we can conclude that our observed size increase was undoubtedly due to the new precursors added.

Figure 3. (A) Upconversion emission spectra obtained after 975 nm excitation for NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ core-only nanoparticles (blue line), and the successive core/shell (green line) and core/shell/shell (black line) structures with NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ in the first shell and undoped NaGdF₄ in the second shell (B) Upconversion emission spectra obtained for NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ core-only nanoparticles (blue line), core/shell (green line) and core/shell/shell (black line) nanoparticles with NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ in the first shell and undoped NaGdF₄ in the second shell. In every case, the nanoparticle concentration is 1 wt% in hexane. On the right side it has been added, a scheme of a core/shell/shell nanoparticle showing the migration mechanism between Yb³⁺ ions, and how it can affect to the emission of the different layers.

To further demonstrate that the new nanostructure we synthesized in fact had a core/shell/shell architecture, we studied the upconversion luminescence properties of the nanoparticles at each successive step of the synthesis. Figure 3A shows the upconverted emission spectrum of each sample after excitation at 975 nm (excitation power density on the focus 2 W/mm²). The electronic 4f transitions responsible for each emission are labeled in the figure, and are schematically shown in Figure 4, both for the Tm³⁺ and Er³⁺ emission bands. According to the generally accepted mechanisms for upconversion in Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺ and Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ systems^{21, 39, 40}, the laser excitation at 975 nm is mainly absorbed by Yb³⁺ ions and then transferred to the co-dopant luminescing ion (Tm³⁺ or Er³⁺), which is playing the role of acceptor in the energy transfer process. Then, in a second step, another Yb³⁺ ion previously excited can transfer its energy to the co-dopant that was excited to the intermediate excited state in the previous step. This process can be repeated several times as long as there is an acceptor ion close enough to the excited Yb³⁺ ions able to accept its energy. In this way,

according to the diagram in Figure 4, it is possible to excite the blue emitting levels of Tm³⁺ in three energy transfer steps (i.e. a 3-photon process), while the green and red emitting levels of Er³⁺ can be excited in two steps (2-photon process). According to Figure 3, also a violet emission band is observed circa 360 nm associated to the ¹D₂ state of Tm³⁺ ions. The population path of this level involves two different mechanisms that occur concomitantly: a fourth energy transfer from Yb³⁺ ions (labeled with an asterisk in Figure 4) and Tm³⁺ to Tm³⁺ energy transfer mechanisms (shown in the supplementary information Figure S2)^{41, 42}.

It is clear from Figure 3A that the core-only nanoparticles obtained in one single microwave step, where only NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ precursors are used, show the characteristic upconverted emissions of Tm³⁺ ions with bands in the violet (around 360 nm, corresponding to ¹D₂ → ³H₆ transition), blue (two bands around 450 nm and 470 nm, corresponding to ¹D₂ → ³F₄ and ¹G₄ → ³H₆ transitions, respectively) and red (around 650 nm, ¹G₄ → ³F₄ transition) ranges. After the growth of the first shell,

described here, which relies on inverting the dopant ions in the core and shell, presents a straightforward and facile method for ascertaining that a core/shell system is in fact present. Furthermore, this method is not limited to upconverting nanoparticles and is easily applicable to other lanthanide-doped systems as long as the co-dopants present different luminescence spectra.

The aforementioned changes in the intensity ratios between the emission bands associated with the Er^{3+} or Tm^{3+} transitions in the blue, green and red regions account for strong differences in the color of the overall emission, i.e. the color of the emitted light that can be seen with the naked eye (Figure 5). To demonstrate these changes, the CIE color coordinates associated to each spectrum in Figure 3 have been calculated, and are depicted in the diagram shown in Figure 6. It is clear from the figure that the $\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ core-only nanoparticles show a green emission color, while the $\text{Tm}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ core-only nanoparticles are associated with a blue emission color. Then, when both ion pairs are incorporated in the same nanoparticle structure albeit spatially separated, different possibilities between these two extremes can be obtained depending on the location of each ion inside the nanoparticle. Moreover, it is also clear that the outer shell in the core/shell/shell architecture, although it is undoped, helps to change the emission color.

Figure 5. Digital images of 1 wt% solutions of upconverting nanoparticles in hexane using an excitation laser source at 975 nm. The pictures have been taken with a Nikon camera (2 s exposition time).

As it has been shown, using this strategy, it is possible to tune the emission color of the upconverting nanoparticles using a single excitation wavelength. Up to that point, though, the range of available colors is restricted to the line shown in Figure 6 between the pure $\text{Er}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ and $\text{Tm}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ -doped core-only nanoparticles ($[\text{Yb}^{3+}] = 20 \text{ mol}\%$, $[\text{Tm}^{3+}] = 0.2 \text{ mol}\%$ and $[\text{Er}^{3+}] = 2 \text{ mol}\%$). Nevertheless, different strategies can be applied to broaden the range of color tuning. For instance, the intensity of the emissions and the intensity ratios between the different emissions will change with doping concentration, changing thus the overall emission color. In the case of Tm^{3+} ions different shades between blue and magenta can be obtained modifying either the Tm^{3+} or Yb^{3+} concentrations³³. In the same way, in the $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}$ area of the nanoparticles, higher Yb^{3+} contents strongly

increase the red emissions coming from Er^{3+} ions compared to the green ones³⁵.

Figure 6. CIE color coordinates obtained from the recorded spectra for $\text{NaGdF}_4:\text{Tm}^{3+}, \text{Yb}^{3+}$ and $\text{NaGdF}_4:\text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Yb}^{3+}$ core-only nanoparticles, the core/shell and the core/shell/shell structures obtained. For the sake of clarity, the data with same Yb^{3+} concentration are linked with dashed black lines.

Thanks to the fact that both pairs of ions are spatially separated in the nanoparticles, these two mentioned dependencies are expected to still work in our case. Otherwise, if Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} ions were doped together in the same host material, they would efficiently transfer energy between themselves. As an example, in Figure 4 some of the possible resonant energy transfer processes between them are marked with grey dashed arrows. These energy transfers between Er^{3+} and Tm^{3+} have been extensively studied in several hosts, both experimentally and theoretically, and it has been demonstrated that the option with a higher probability takes place between the lowest excited-state levels ($^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ (Er^{3+}): $^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow ^3\text{F}_4$ (Tm^{3+})) and accounts for the depopulation of Er^{3+} ions to populate Tm^{3+} ions²³⁻²⁶. Such a modification in these low energy states that are at the root of every upconversion process, results in an intensification of the emissions from Tm^{3+} ions in detriment of Er^{3+} ones. This, in terms of emission “color” means that blue light is generally obtained, or depending on the concentration of dopants and on the presence of Yb^{3+} ions, white light is also achievable^{35, 49-53}. Nevertheless, as a further test, particles with the three dopants mixed together have been synthesized, and are discussed in the supplementary information (Figure S5).

In this work, to further explore the possibilities that the core/shell or core/shell/shell nanostructures offer in terms of emission color management the selected strategy has been to change Yb^{3+} concentration in the $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}$ area of the particles. Thus, samples with different $\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+}$ content have been prepared ($\text{Yb}^{3+}/\text{Er}^{3+} = 20$

mol%/2 mol%; 60 mol%/2 mol%; 90 mol%/2 mol%) while Yb³⁺/Tm³⁺ concentration has been kept constant (Yb³⁺/Tm³⁺ = 20 mol%/0.2 mol%). The CIE coordinates calculated from the emission spectra of the two new families of nanoparticles are shown in Figure 6 (the upconverted emission spectra can be seen in the Figure S7). Also, to offer a visual example of the obtained results, in Figure 5 a digital photograph of some of the samples excited with 975 nm light is shown. It should be noted that we performed an XRD analysis of the sample heavily doped with Yb³⁺ to determine if any changes in the crystalline structure were present, which could affect the luminescence (see Figure S6). Both samples show equivalent patterns, indicating that they both crystallized in the cubic phase. Nevertheless, due to the different size of Gd³⁺ and Yb³⁺ ions, the diffraction peaks are slightly shifted when the concentration of Yb³⁺ is increased.

First of all, it is clear that the emission of the Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ core-only nanoparticles (from Figure 6) that an increase of Yb³⁺ concentration pushes the overall observed emission of the Er³⁺ ions towards the red, as it was expected³⁵. Then, the addition of the different layers, first the Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺-doped one and then the undoped NaGdF₄ one, add a blue contribution to the spectra that brings the emission color closer to the white, although depending on the starting Yb³⁺ concentration of the core, the actual emission color ranges from cyan (for [Yb³⁺] = 20 mol%) to pink (for [Yb³⁺] = 90 mol%). In any case, when the positions of the dopants change and Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺ ions are moved to the core, the emission color moves to blue since the Tm³⁺ contribution is now stronger than the NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ shell.

Therefore, it is clear that using a core/shell strategy it is possible to exploit independently the luminescent possibilities of the Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ and Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺ ion pairs while minimizing the Er³⁺-Tm³⁺ cross-talk. This opens the path to a broad range of emission tuning possibilities. In terms of color, and for the dopants and concentrations chosen in this work, this range goes from green to red and to blue, including all the intermediate hues, and always using 975 nm excitation.

In conclusion, NaGdF₄:Tm³⁺, Yb³⁺ and NaGdF₄:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ ultrasmall homogeneous upconverting nanoparticles with doped and undoped shells have been synthesized following a microwave based thermolysis procedure. The formation of core/shell and core/shell/shell nanoarchitectures using this technique allows the doping with both pairs of dopants, spatially separated into the particles. Then, it has been demonstrated that depending on the position of the dopants inside the nanoparticle architecture, the intensity ratios of the different emission bands change, and thus, the overall emission color is different in each case. Exploiting the fact that Er³⁺-Tm³⁺ cross-talk is minimized in the proposed structure (due to their spatial segregation), and therefore the luminescent properties of the Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ and Tm³⁺/Yb³⁺ ion pairs can be exploited separately, it has been shown that it is possible to tune the overall emission color of the luminescence keeping the excitation wavelength constant at 975 nm.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information Available. Further details on the synthesis, morphology and optical characterization on every family of nanoparticles used throughout this paper can be found in the Supporting Information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

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